

**SYNTHETIC INVESTIGATIONS IN THE FUSED RING SYSTEMS.
PART I. STUDIES ON THE MICHAEL CONDENSATION
BETWEEN ETHYL *CYCLOPENTANONE*-2-CARBO-
XYLATE AND DIETHYL MALEATE**

BY (LATE) K. C. GHOSH

Michael condensation between ethyl *cyclopentanone*-2-carboxylate and diethyl maleate has been studied with different condensing agents.

In this paper, the observations that have been made while carrying out the Michael condensation between *cyclopentanone* carboxylate and maleic ester have been described. The condensation was first carried out between *cyclopentanone* carboxylate and maleic ester with a small quantity of potassium ethoxide in the cold in an ether-alcoholic solution. Yield of the higher boiling product, thus obtained, was almost quantitative. From the analytical data, it cannot be decided whether the condensation takes place normally to yield the β -ketic system (I) or the tetra-ester (II).

To determine the constitution of the condensation product it has been hydrolysed with concentrated hydrochloric acid and the gummy acid obtained has been esterified. The ester thus formed is found to have the same boiling point and combustion data as of the original condensation product. Further, the tetra-ester (II) undergoes Dieckmann condensation on treatment with sodium dust. The ring-closure can take place in two ways, leading to the formation of either a five-membered (III) or a six-membered (IV) system. The β -ketic ester is hydrolysed

with concentrated hydrochloric acid when a solid keto-acid is obtained; the latter is esterified. The acid or its ester may be represented by either (V) or (VI).

[V, R-H or Et]

[VI, R-H or Et]

*cyclo*Pentanone carboxylate has been condensed with maleic ester in presence of piperidine. The boiling point of the condensation product is found to be lower than that of the condensation product obtained when potassium ethoxide is used as the condensing agent. The yield of the condensation product in this case is satisfactory; further, the unchanged materials can be recovered and recondensed with piperidine. The condensation product is hydrolysed with concentrated hydrochloric acid when a solid keto-acid is obtained. This acid has been found to be identical with the solid acid derived from the hydrolysis of the β -keto ester obtained by the cyclisation of the tetra-ester (II). The acid has been esterified and the ester and its semicarbazone are also found to be identical with the di-ester (V) or (VI), and its semicarbazone.

Finally *cyclopentanone* carboxylate has been condensed with maleic ester in presence of a trace of sodium ethoxide. The condensation product, obtained in very poor yield, has a boiling point lower than that of the condensation product obtained by the use of potassium ethoxide as the condensing agent. The condensation product on hydrolysis with concentrated hydrochloric acid also yields a solid keto-acid which is found to be identical with the acid obtained by the hydrolysis of (i) the β -keto ester (III or IV) and (ii) the condensation product obtained using piperidine as the condensing agent. The ester of this acid and its semicarbazone are found to be identical with the di-ester (V) or (VI) and its semicarbazone.

In view of the above results, it is concluded that the condensation between ethyl *cyclopentanone* carboxylate and maleic ester in presence of a trace of sodium ethoxide and piperidine proceeds in the normal manner to yield the Michael product (I), but in presence of potassium ethoxide (0.1M) the tetra-ester (II) is formed. Further, this ester (II) on cyclisation by means of sodium yields the five membered β -keto ring system (III).

The investigation of the above reactions was undertaken with a view to synthesising the pyroketo acid (VII) obtained by Wieland *et al.*, through the oxidative degradation of deoxycholic acid. It seems that the β -keto ester (III) is eminently suitable as a starting material for such a synthesis. It was expected that the $C_4H_9CO_2H$ group belonging to (VII) could be introduced by reacting the above β -keto ester with the appropriate ester halide followed by hydrolysis. Further, it is intended to introduce the necessary angular methyl group by reacting the keto-ester derivative with magnesium methyl iodide followed by dehy-

dration, hydrolysis and final ring-closure. Above series of reactions may be schematically represented as follows :

As a preliminary to the above objective, Grignard complex of methyl iodide has been reacted with the keto-ester (V). On working up the reaction product a lactone, probably (VIII), is obtained. It has, however, not been possible to convert (VIII) into the required unsaturated acid (IX) due to the easy formation of the lactone even in the cold. Further treatment of the lactonic ester (VIII) with baryta with subsequent reaction of the dry barium salt with PCl_5 , followed by treatment with stannic chloride in carbon disulphide solution in the cold, according to the method of Haberland (*Ber*, 1939, 72 1221, 1226), did not yield the desired ketonic product.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Ethyl n-Hexane-1 : 2 : 3 : 6-tetracarboxylate.—Potassium (0.4 g.) was pulverised under xylene, xylene was replaced by ether and cooled in a freezing mixture.

Alcohol (55 c.c.) was added and when all the potassium had reacted with alcohol, a mixture of *cyclopentanone* carboxylate (15.6 g.) and maleic ester (17.2 g.) was added and the reaction mixture after keeping for 3 days at the room temperature, was poured into ice-cold acidulated water. The precipitated oil was extracted with ether, the extract well washed with water, dried and the ether removed. The residue was distilled, when hardly any unchanged material could be obtained and the distillate boiled at $182^{\circ}/4\text{mm}$, yield 36 g. [Found: C, 58.0; H, 7.86 $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_8$ (II) requires C, 57.7; H, 8.02 per cent and $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_7$ (I) requires C, 58.5; H, 7.32 per cent].

The above product was refluxed with 150 c. c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid for 12 hours. The clear aqueous solution was evaporated to dryness on a water-bath. The thick syrupy liquid was then esterified by refluxing with 100 c. c. of alcohol and 12 c. c. of concentrated sulphuric acid for 24 hours. The product after dilution with cold water was extracted with ether and the ethereal solution was washed with water, bicarbonate solution and water again. Ether was removed and the residue was distilled at $182\text{--}83^{\circ}/4\text{ mm.}$, yield 30 g. (Found: C, 57.9; H, 7.87. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_8$ requires C, 57.7; H, 8.02 per cent).

Ethyl 2-Keto-3-carbethoxycyclopentylsuccinate.—The above tetra-basic ester (II, 20 g.) was refluxed with sodium dust (2.8 g.) in dry benzene till the bright surface of sodium could not be detected. The cooled reaction mixture was treated with ice and hydrochloric acid. The benzene layer was separated, washed with water, sodium bicarbonate solution and again with water, solvent removed and distilled in vacuum, b. p. $165\text{--}70^{\circ}/4\text{ mm.}$, yield 21 g. (Found: C, 58.2; H, 7.30. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_7$ requires C, 58.5; H, 7.32 per cent). It gave a positive ferric reaction.

Ethyl 2-Ketocyclopentylsuccinate.—The above β -keto ester was hydrolysed by refluxing with 100 c. c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid for 24 hours and the whole mass was transferred to a porcelain basin and evaporated to dryness when a solid acid was obtained. On crystallisation from benzene it melted at $134\text{--}36^{\circ}$, after shrinking at 120° . (Found: C, 53.6; H, 5.96. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 54.0; H, 6.0 per cent).

The acid was esterified by refluxing with alcohol (50 c. c.) and sulphuric acid (6 c. c.) for 24 hours. On working up in the usual way the product distilled at $155\text{--}60^{\circ}/5\text{ mm.}$, yield 10 g. The *semicarbazone* was prepared by warming two drops of this ester with an alcoholic solution of semicarbazide hydrochloride and sodium acetate. On crystallisation from aqueous alcohol, it melted at 118° . (Found: C, 60.6; H, 7.80. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 60.9; H, 7.81 per cent).

Ethyl 1-Carboxy-2-ketocyclopentylsuccinate.—(a) A mixture of *cyclopentanone* carboxylate (60 g.) and maleic ester (66 g.) was taken in a flask fitted with a cork and calcium chloride guard tube, and to the mixture were added 20 c. c. of piperidine when the mixture became quite hot. It was heated on a water-bath for 16 hours, cooled and poured into iced hydrochloric acid. The oil was extracted

with ether and washed with water, dried and ether removed and the residue distilled. The fraction boiling at $165-70^{\circ}/5$ mm. was collected, yield 75 g. The unchanged material can be recondensed with piperidine to obtain further quantities of the condensation product. (Found : C, 58.2 ; H 7.38 $C_{16}H_{24}O_7$ requires C, 58.5 ; H, 7.32 per cent).

The above ester (75 g.) was refluxed with 300 c. c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid for 36 hours. The hydrolysed product was evaporated to dryness in a porcelain basin on a water-bath when the same solid acid (V) was obtained. This acid was esterified by refluxing with alcohol (200 c. c.) and sulphuric acid (24 c. c.) for 36 hours. On working up, the product distilled at $155-60^{\circ}/5$ mm., yield 39 g. It gave a semicarbazone of m.p. 113° which was found to be identical with the semicarbazone of (V). (Found : C, 60.6 ; H, 7.76. $C_{16}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 60.9 ; H, 7.81 per cent).

(b) *cyclopentanone* carboxylate (15.6 g.) in alcohol (33 c. c.) was added to a well cooled solution of a trace of sodium ethoxide dissolved in alcohol (10 c. c.). The mixture was cooled in a freezing mixture. Then another solution of maleic ester (17.2 g.) in alcohol (20 c. c.) was cooled and added to the previously cooled mixture and the whole thing was left overnight. On working up, only 5 g. of the high boiling product ($165-170^{\circ}/5$ mm.) were obtained. (Found : C, 58.0 ; H, 7.36. $C_{16}H_{24}O_7$ requires C, 58.5 ; H, 7.32 per cent).

The above ester was hydrolysed by refluxing with 40 c. c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid for 24 hours. On evaporation of the hydrolysed product the solid keto-acid (V) was obtained. The acid was esterified with 25 c. c. of alcohol and 3 c. c. concentrated sulphuric acid ; on working up in the usual way 2.5 g. of the distillate (b.p. $155-60^{\circ}/5$ mm.) were obtained. It gave a semicarbazone, m.p. 118° (mixed m.p. with the semicarbazone of the ester, V). (Found : C, 61.0 H, 7.79. $C_{13}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 60.9 ; H, 7.81 per cent).

Lactone of 2-Methyl-2-hydroxycyclopentylsuccinic Semiethyl Ester-acid.—Methyl iodide (8 c.c.) was dropped slowly and carefully on 2.3 g. of magnesium in absolute ether (30 c. c.). After the reaction was complete, 20 g. of the keto-ester, diluted with dry ether, were taken in a flask, cooled in an ice-bath. The Grignard's complex in ether was added dropwise, when white solids separated ; the whole mass was kept overnight. It was decomposed with iced hydrochloric acid, extracted with ether, the ethereal layer was washed with water and cold dilute NaOH solution and next with water. The ethereal layer was dried, the solvent was removed and distilled, b.p. $160^{\circ}/4$ mm., yield 10.1 g.

By the above reaction, the tertiary alcohol might have been formed ; but the analytical data (given below) did not correspond with the alcohol but with the lactone (VII). This lactone was found to be insoluble in cold dilute NaOH solution. (Found : C, 63.2 ; H, 7.92. $C_{12}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 63.7 ; H, 7.96 per cent).

Hydrolysis of the Lactone (VIII) and an attempt for Ring-closure.—The above lactone (5 g.) was refluxed with baryta solution (28 g.) and the barium salt formed was dried and treated with PCl_5 (19 g.) in dry carbon disulphide, followed by treatment with stannous chloride (125 c. c.) in a freezing mixture. The reaction mixture was decomposed with ice; organic layer separated, washed with water, dried and the solvent removed. But the desired product could not be isolated from the residue.

Thanks are due to Prof. P. C. Mitter and Prof. S. N. Bose for their interest and to Dr. D. K. Banerjee for generous help during the progress of this work. Thanks are also due to Mr. N. Ghosh for micro-analyses of some of the compounds.

SIR P. C. RAY RESEARCH FELLOW'S LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE AND
TECHNOLOGY, CALCUTTA.

Received June 18, 1948.
